

Served or Abused? A Cadence–Control–Calculus Framework of Perceived Exploitation in Artificial Intelligence–Driven Data Capture

Online Supplementary Material A: Measurement Details.

Construct / Item	Dimension	Item Statements	Scale	Source
<i>Perceived Exploitation</i>				
DIS1	Distrust	<i>It will exploit users' vulnerability given the chance</i>	1–7 Likert (SD–SA)	Cho (2006)
DIS2	Distrust	<i>It will engage in damaging and harmful behavior toward users to pursue the company's interests</i>	1–7 Likert (SD–SA)	Cho (2006)
DIS3	Distrust	<i>It is irresponsible and untrustworthy</i>	1–7 Likert (SD–SA)	Cho (2006)
DIS4	Distrust	<i>It will treat users in a deceptive and fraudulent manner</i>	1–7 Likert (SD–SA)	Cho (2006)
CTRL1	Lack of Control	<i>It allows me to control how my data are used</i>	1–7 Likert (SD–SA)	Webster <i>et al.</i> (1993)
CTRL2	Lack of Control	<i>Using this data capture method, I feel in control</i>	1–7 Likert (SD–SA)	Webster <i>et al.</i> (1993)
RISK1	Perceived Risk	<i>I dread that my personal information will be collected and used</i>	1–7 Likert (SD–SA)	Demoulin & Zidda (2009)
RISK2	Perceived Risk	<i>I fear that the platform will use my personal data for commercial purposes</i>	1–7 Likert (SD–SA)	Demoulin & Zidda (2009)
RISK3	Perceived Risk	<i>I'm not confident about how my personal information will be used</i>	1–7 Likert (SD–SA)	Demoulin & Zidda (2009)
<i>Preference for Data Capture Cadence</i>				
PREF1	-	<i>On a 1–6 scale, where 1 = intermittent data capture and 6 = continuous data capture, which data capture frequency would you choose given the context presented above?</i>	1–6 (1=intermittent; 6=continuous)	Developed for this study

Perceived value-for-data exchange

PVDE1	-	<i>I feel that the amount of information collected about me is justified by the quality and relevance of the content provided to me</i>	1–7 Likert (SD–SA)	Developed for this study
<i>Experience With AI</i>				
EXP1	-	<i>I consider myself highly knowledgeable about artificial intelligence technologies</i>	1–7 Likert (SD–SA)	Muehling <i>et al.</i> (1990)
EXP2	-	<i>I consider myself an expert in using artificial intelligence technologies</i>	1–7 Likert (SD–SA)	Muehling <i>et al.</i> (1990)
<i>Attitude Toward AI</i>				
ATT1	-	<i>Bad – Good</i>	1–7 Semantic Differential	MacKenzie & Lutz (1989)
ATT2	-	<i>Dislike – Like</i>	1–7 Semantic Differential	MacKenzie & Lutz (1989)
ATT3	-	<i>Negative – Positive</i>	1–7 Semantic Differential	MacKenzie & Lutz (1989)
ATT4	-	<i>Unfavorable – Favorable</i>	1–7 Semantic Differential	MacKenzie & Lutz (1989)

*Control items were reverse-coded so higher scores indicate greater lack of control.

Sources:

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